

KAAF UNIVERSITY COLLEGE
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONIC ENGINEERING

TOPIC
AUTOMATIC ROOM TEMPERATURE CONTROL

A Proposal Submitted to The Faculty of Engineering, Department of Electrical and Electronic, KAAF University College in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Award of Bachelor of Science Degree in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my own original work and that no part of it has been presented for another degree in this university or elsewhere.

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Dedications

I dedicate this work to the almighty God for his divine intervention, divine guidance, divine strength and divine protection to complete this project. And I also dedicate this work to my father and mother, Mr Adenekan Michael and Mrs Adenekan Theresa for their constant prayers, encouragement, support and for believing in me even when I did not believe in myself.

“Michael Godwin”

I dedicate this work to the almighty God for his divine intervention and to my wife, Ampadu Comfort for her believing in me, encouraging me and supporting me in and constantly praying for me.

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ABSTRACT

The issue of instability of room temperature is a major issue to homes, industries and institutions. The normal room temperature is 25°C, however due to unfavourable weather condition the temperature can be high or low. The conventional method of controlling a room temperature using manual regulation method causes problem like, discomfort to user's due to the manual regulation of room heating or cooling medium when a high or low temperature occurs. The purposes of this project are to design a fully automated room temperature control system, to design a temperature controller using a microcontroller to write an algorithm to controller a room temperature and to analyse the performance of the room temperature automated system.

We achieved these aims by building a system which mainly consist of a fan, a bulb to represent a heater, a temperature sensor, a thermal sensor and most in importantly a microcontroller. We implemented an algorithm in the system using a microcontroller which will instruct the fan and heater (bulb) when to activate or deactivate and when to change their speed in the case of fan and when to change their heating level in the case of a heater.

The result obtained from our analyses proof the effectiveness of our project on how the temperature control was achieved by automatically controlling the room heating and cooling unit.

Keywords: Microcontroller, fan, heater, temperature sensor, thermal sensor

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Today in our daily life we experience changes in temperature in different hours of the day either hot or cold and we try to control the temperature with either a fan, an air-condition or a heater. But all the turning on, off and control of the room cooling and heating mediums is done manually each time there is a change in temperature, which can be an arduous task for the user and the regulator can incur damages due to repeatedly changing of fan speed if the room cooler is a fan. Therefore, this manual method of controlling temperature has caused a lot of problems in the world today. For instance, during the late hours of the night the metabolic rate of one's body decreases and the room temperature tends to change to either low or high depending on the weather condition, when that happens, it is imperative that the room cooling medium or heating medium should be regulated to suit the temperature condition of the room but with the manual system of regulation, regulation of a room cooling medium or heating medium cannot be achieved at night when the temperature changes, because the regulator operator or user will be asleep. Furthermore, the disabled / physically challenged persons are affected the most by the manual system of regulation because of the inconveniences associated in changing the cooling and heating medium speed or level manually. In the manual system of regulation, there are times the user forgets to switch off the cooling or heating medium while being away thereby making the heating or cooling medium to be in operation continuously which is considered to be a waste of energy and thus leads to a higher electricity bill. Therefore, the ingenuity of the stated problems of the manual control of room temperature is to regulate the cooling and heating medium automatically and automatically switch off the cooling or heating medium when the room is not occupied. The automatic regulation of cooling and heating

medium helps control the temperature of a room by automatically regulating the heating and cooling medium in accordance's to the temperature of a room. This system eliminates the problems of human energy consumption of manually regulating the room cooler and heater when the temperature changes and even wastages of electrical energy problems.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Nowadays, the demand for accurate temperature control and air freshening control has conquered many of industrial domains such as process heat, automotive, industrial places or office buildings where the air is cooled in order to maintain a comfortable environment for its occupants. One of the important concerns in low temperature areas and high temperature areas is the desired temperature achievement and consumption optimization [1]. Basically, cooling mediums are operated manually with the help of regulators (if it a fan) as the temperature changes. Any change in the temperature will not give any change in the level or speed of the cooling medium except the user change the speed or level manually and this require a repeatedly extra effort for regulating the fan speed which acts as burden to the user [1]. Conventional methods of regulating cooling and heating medium are done using a switch with difference speed or adjustments in the case of an electric fan being use as a cooling medium, the regulator which is a switch has four or six point which indicate the speeds depending on the design. They are speed 0, speed 1, speed 2 and speed 3, or speed 0, speed 1, speed 2, speed 3, speed 4 and speed 5. The speed 0 is especially for switching off the Fan. The slowest is for speed 1 and the fastest is speed 3 or speed 5 in that order. another problem associated with the manual regulation of the cooling and heating medium is energy wastage. At times users unknowingly forget to switch off the room heating or cooling medium which can lead to waste of energy.

Contemporary automatic regulation of cooling and heating medium in accordance's to the temperature of a room uses microcontroller as the brain of the automatic system and temperature sensor to measure the room temperature. The microcontroller is use to set a reference temperature value for the system and instruct the cooling and heating medium when to activate, deactivate and change in levels. While the temperature sensor measures the temperature of the room and send the measured temperature value to the microcontroller to cross-references the measured temperature value to the reference temperature value. When the measured temperature value is less than the reference temperature value the microcontroller sends a signal to the room heating medium to get activated, in the reverse situation the microcontroller sends a signal to activate the room cooling medium [2]. Therefore, making the system automatic and free from user control. Though the contemporary method of regulating room cooling and heating medium is an excellent design, it lacks the solution to the aforementioned problem of users unknowingly or knowingly leaving the room cooling or heating medium ON when the room is not occupied, when that happens energy is wasted. [3]. It is imperative that the electrical energy is utilize in a decent manner.

1.3 Problem Statement

The issue of instability of room temperature is a major issue to homes, industries and institutions. The normal room temperature is 25°C, however due to unfavourable weather condition the temperature can be high or low. The conventional method of controlling a room temperature using manual regulation method causes problem like, discomfort to user's dues to the manual regulation of room heating or cooling medium when a high or low temperature occurs. Furthermore, at late hours of the day when occupant of a room is asleep the ambient temperature tends to get low due to the weather condition at that period, the low ambient temperature can be harmful to the occupant of the room which can lead to illness [4]. The healthy human body maintains its internal temperature around 37°C. Variations, usually of less than 1°C, occur with

the time of the day, level of physical activity or emotional state [5]. A change of body temperature of more than 1°C occurs only during illness or when environmental conditions are more than the body's ability to cope with extreme heat [5]. As the environment warms-up, the body tends to warm-up as well. The body's internal "thermostat" maintains a constant inner body temperature by pumping more blood to the skin and by increasing sweat production [5]. In this way, the body increases the rate of heat loss to balance the heat burden [5]. In a very hot environment, the rate of "heat gain" is more than the rate of "heat loss" and the body temperature begins to rise. A rise in the body temperature results in heat illnesses [5].

In a cold environment, most of the body's energy is used to keep the internal body temperature warm [5]. Over time, the body will begin to shift blood flow from the extremities (hands, feet, arms, and legs) and outer skin to the core (chest and abdomen) [5]. This allows exposed skin and the extremities to cool rapidly and increases the risk of frostbite [5]. When the body can no longer maintain core temperature by constricting blood vessels, it shivers to increase heat production [5]. Maximum severe shivering develops when the body temperature has fallen to 35°C (95°F) [5]. Hypothermia becomes an issue at this point [5].

1.4 Motivation

We were motivated to do this proposed project when we notice how the temperature condition of a room can change unpredictably at day and night and the room cooling or heating medium need to be regulated to stabilize the room temperature to a suitable degree for the occupants in the room but because of the manual system of regulation it will be arduous for the occupant of the room to wake up from sleep or suspend his/her activities in the room each time there is a change in temperature to regulate the cooling or heating medium and also because of the dangers of excess high and low temperature to the human body. Therefore, the idea of constructing an automatic room temperature control was conceived.

1.5 Objective

- To design a fully automated room temperature control system
- To design a temperature controller using a microcontroller
- To write an algorithm to controller a room temperature
- To analyse the performance of the room temperature automated system

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays there are various methods of controlling room temperature for instead proportional integral and derivative controller (PID) and more are still be improved. This chapter reviewed pervious implementations and strategies in the field of controlling room temperature by using various methods.

2.2 Proportional Integral and Derivative controller (PID)

The majority of control systems in the world are operated using Proportional Integral and Derivative controllers (PID) [6]. The PI control algorithm offers some of the advantages of both the proportional and integral algorithms [7]. The main process of PID algorithm controller is parameter tuning, tuning in essence is through changing the regulator parameters to match the characteristics of properties and processes in order to improve the dynamic and static index system, so as to achieve the best control effect parameters [8]. It is more difficult to tune a PID controller because of the gains to be adjusted [6]. The systems in [6] and [8] make use of PID controllers. PID controller were implement in [6], [9] and [8]

2.3 Fuzzy Logic Controller

The Fuzzy method gives a human like intuition to the control strategy and is self-tolerant to inputs which are no so precise [10]. Fuzzy logic controller (FLC) uses the qualitative knowledge of a system to design a controller. FLC deals with the uncertainties in the process of control by collecting both human knowledge and expertise [11]. The Fuzzy Logic Controller contains different components like Fuzzification, Defuzzification and Fuzzy Rule inference [10]. To implement fuzzy logic technique to a real application requires the following three steps: [12]

1. Fuzzification – convert classical data or crisp data into fuzzy data or Membership Functions (MFs)
2. Fuzzy Inference Process – combine membership functions with the control rules to derive the fuzzy output
3. Defuzzification – use different methods to calculate each associated output and put them into a table: the lookup table. Pick up the output from the lookup table based on the current input during an application.

System using fuzzy logic controller were done in [13], [10] and [12]

2.4 MICROCONTROLLER

A microcontroller is a computer control system on a single chip. It has many electronic circuits built into it which can decode written instructions and convert them to electrical signals [1]. The microcontroller step through these instructions and execute them one after the other. Microcontroller uses Instructions sets (program) to wire the gates electronically to perform some function instead of hard wiring a number of logic gates together [1]. Therefore, a microcontroller can be used to control the fan speed according to the temperature of the room [1]. [2], [14] and [1] Make use of the microcontroller technology to achieved the control of temperature in a room

2.5 PROGRAMABLE LOGIC CONTROLLER(PLC)

PLC is an electronic computer that can perform various functions in the control of complex levels [15]. PLC is generally depicted with lines and equipment on a ladder diagram [15]. PLC can operate all systems that have the output is to be on or off and systems with varying output [15]. Therefore, making the PLC an ideal controller to control temperature. PLC technology have been used in various project, and it is also an ideal means for the control of room temperature. project in [15] made use of PLC in the control of room temperature.

2.6 Summary of the Pervious systems

The project done in [1] the temperature is controlled by varying the speed of an electric fan.

By varying the speed of an electric fan temperature control can be achieved but only from a higher value of temperature to a lower value, in the event when the temperature value becomes low the system used in [1] cannot achieve the control of temperature from a lower value to a higher value. Therefore, the temperature during that event will not be controlled and the room will remain very cold because the system in [1] cannot vary the temperature. The system used in [16] is much improved than the system used in [1], [16] system employ new improvement of controlling temperature to [1] system. One of the improvements in the system of [16] is overcoming the challenge faced in [1] system in the event of low temperature. The system in [16] overcomes the early challenge in [1] by employing a heating medium which will be activated in the event of a low temperature. Also, the system in [16] employs settings to keep the room temperature at 20 °C and 28 °C, which are one of the improvements to the system in [1]. System in [16] is an improvement of the system in [1] because the system in [16] control system can monitor the conditions night and day with immediate response to any changes. By controlling actuators such as heater or cooling fan, it is able to provide a favourable environment for the home automatically. Furthermore, the system in [2] makes other improvements to the systems in [1] and [16]. The system done in [2] employed ON-OFF type controller. Here the set value for temperature can be externally set by user. If it exceeds the set value the heater is turned off. After then when temperature falls below the specified limit again heater is turned on.

Pervious systems only activate the cooling and heating medium without controlling the speed or level, the pervious system which tried to control the level or speed of the heating and cooling medium used relays which makes the system more sophisticated which can lead to difficulties in troubleshooting, also some pervious systems used single relay to activate both the heating and cooling medium which makes the relay a point of failure for the heating and cooling

medium. In addition, some pervious system controlled a room temperature by making use of multiple cooling mediums for example fans without a heating medium.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter present the development of the automatic room temperature control.

3.2 METHOD

System main sections

- Power Unit
- Sensing Unit
- Control Unit
- Output Unit

3.2.1 Power unit

A 9V battery is used as power supply to the system, a L7805CV voltage regulator is use to step down the voltage from the 9V battery to 5VDC which provide a constant 5VDC supply to the components that requires 5V such as microcontroller, LM35 temperature sensor, Passive infra-red thermal sensor and keypad. Therefore, voltage regulator is connected to the microcontroller, temperature sensor, thermal sensor and keypad. The L7805CV voltage regulator has an output voltage of 5V and an output current of 1.5A. Fig3-1 shown the block diagram of the power unit of the circuit indicating the connections.

Fig 3-1: Block diagram of the power section of the circuit.

3.2.2 Sensing section

The system used a LM35 temperature sensor to measure the temperature in the room and a passive inferred sensor (PIR sensor) to detect the present of human in the room by detecting their heat signature. The LM35 temperature sensor measures the temperature of the room and communicate to the microcontroller with the measured temperature in form of voltage, the

measured temperature in the LM35 is proportional to the output voltage of LM35. Therefore,

10mv is equal 1°C [17]. The LM35 temperature sensor temperature range is -55°C to 150°C, the operation voltages are 4V-30V [17] but operating with 5V in this project and the LM35 current drain is less than 60µA [17]. The PIR sensor communicate with the microcontroller

Fig3-2: Block diagram explaining the sensing section of the circuit.

when the room is occupied by a person and not occupied by a person. Furthermore, the PIR sensor operate with 5V and less than 100uA current. The LM35 temperature sensor output terminal is connected to an analogue pin in the microcontroller and the input terminal of the LM35 is connected to the voltage regulator. The input terminal of the PIR sensor is connected to the voltage regulator to receive 5VDC from the voltage regulator and the output terminal of the PIR sensor is connected to an analogue pin in the microcontroller. Fig3-2 shows the block diagram of the sensing unit of the circuit indicating the connections.

3.2.3 Control section

An Atmega328p microcontroller is used to control the system which is the heart of the entire system, the microcontroller is clocked by the crystal oscillator as it does not have an internal clock. A crystal oscillator is an electronic oscillator circuit that uses the mechanical resonance of a vibrating crystal of piezoelectric material to create an electrical signal with a constant frequency [18]. This frequency is often used to keep track of time, as in quartz wristwatches, to provide a stable clock signal for digital integrated circuits, and to stabilize frequencies for radio transmitters and receivers [18]. Therefore, the power pin of the microcontroller which is pin 7 is connected to the 5V voltage regulator and the fan and the heater optotriac are connected to pin 17 and 15 of the microcontroller respectively because those are some of the pins in the microcontroller that performs PWM, the other components are connected to any other digital or analogue pins on the microcontroller. Connected to other pins of the microcontroller are: LM35 temperature sensor, PIR thermal sensor, 16x2 LCD, a zero-crossing detector and a keypad. The microcontroller controls the speed of the fan and level of the heater by a means of

pulse width modulation (PWM). Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) is a method to manipulate the width of signal in the form of pulse in a period, to obtain different average voltages [19]. Microcontroller is capable of performing pulse width modulation. Therefore, the Microcontroller controlled the speed of the fan and the level of heater by sending pulses of signal to the gate of the triac and varying the duty cycle (Duration of wave) of the applied plus. Duty cycle describes the proportion of 'on' time to the regular interval or 'period' of time; a low duty cycle corresponds to low power, because the power is off for most of the time [19], When the duty cycle is varied speed controlled can be achieved because the wave width is proportional to the duty cycle [20]. These pulses of signal widths changes in accordance to the differences in measured temperature and references temperature. The fan output (speed) and output of the heater (level) is based on the level of pulses sent to the them. When controlling an AC load, it is important to switch on the load at the zero-crossing point which is the point in an AC wave when the wave is at zero value when no voltage is flowing. If the AC load is not control or switched at the zero-crossing point, a current spike will be created through the load which will cause electron magnetic interferences. In other to avoid current spike when switching the AC loads (Fan and heater) a zero-crossing detector is use in the system, Fig3-4 shows the zero-crossing detector circuit. The zero-crossing detector is use to detect the zero-crossing point of the AC waveform. The zero-crossing detector in the system helps the system to generate sync wave to that of an AC. The zero-crossing detector is connected to the microcontroller analogue pin. Fig3-3 shows the block diagram explaining the control section of the circuit.

Fig 3-3: Block diagram explaining the control section of the circuit.

3.2.4 Outputs unit

The Fan, the heater and the liquid crystal display (LCD) are the outputs of the system. The fan is an AC axial fan, an incandescent lamp is use as a representation of the heater in the system. The fan and lamp are supply by a 220/240 AC voltage source gotten from a socket outlet, while LCD is power by the 5V voltage regulator. The fan and heater are connected to the microcontroller via triac and optotriac. Two triacs (BTA16) [one for the fan the other for the heater] and a MOC3011 Optotriacs are connected between the output unit (fan and heater) and the microcontroller. The triacs are used in the system to regulate the speed of the fan automatically and regulated the heater automatically, a resistor and capacitor are connected to the triacs. The capacitor will limit the rise of voltage across the triacs and the resistor limit the surge of current from the capacitor when the triac fires and damp the ringing of the capacitance with load inductance. The optotriacs are connected to the triacs to isolate the AC source neural from the DC source neutral to private the circuit board from electrocuting when touched. If the AC neutral is connected to the DC neutral, when the system is energized the nonconductive part of the circuit board will be conductive which can lead to electric stock when the board is touched. The MOC3011 Optotriac consists of gallium arsenide infrared

emitting diodes, optically coupled to silicon bilateral switch and are designed for applications requiring isolated triac triggering, low-current isolated ac switching, high electrical isolation (to 7500 Vac peak), high detector standoff voltage [21]. A triac is a bilateral device, designated by MT1, MT2 and Gate (G) [22]. Where MT1 and MT2 are the current carrying terminals, the gate terminal is use for triggering the triac [22]. The triac will conduct in either direction and can be triggered with a positive or negative gate signal [22]. In an inductive load such motors, when the current falls below the holding current I_H (The current require to keep the triac in conduction mode) the triac cease to conduct, but there exists a certain voltage which must appear across the triac. If this voltage appears too rapidly, the triac will resume conduction and control is lost, in order to achieve control with the inductive load, the rate of rise of voltage $\left(\frac{dv}{dt}\right)$ must be limited by a RC (Resistor and Capacitor) network across the triac [22]. The capacitor of the RC network will then limit the $\left(\frac{dv}{dt}\right)$ across the triac and the resistor is necessary to limit the surge of current from the capacitor when the triac fires and damp the ringing of the capacitor with the load inductance [22]. The LCD is an electronic display module, it is use for the purpose of displaying the measured temperature and the reference temperature, also the LCD is used to display the speed and level of the fan and heater. The reference temperature can be set by the user via a keypad. The system make use of a 16x2 LCD which mean the LCD can display 16 characters in two rows. Figure (14) shows the system circuit and figure (15) shows the block diagram of the entire system explain the parts of the system.

Fig 3-4: Zero crossing detector circuit.

Fig 3-5: System circuit diagram

Fig 3-6: The block diagram of the system explaining the circuit.

3.3 Implementation

The microcontroller is programmed with C programming language using Arduino Uno Integrated environment (IDE), Fig3-6 shown the flow chart of the microcontroller algorithm.

Therefore, Figure (17) shows the ATmega 328p microcontroller to Arduino Uno pin mapping.

When the zero-crossing detector detect the zero-crossing point of an AC wave in the system, it communicates with the microcontroller, which will allow the microcontroller to control the output unit safely. The microcontroller sends pulses of signal to the gate of the triac and varies these pulses of signals to control the speed of the fan and level of the heat from the heater.

When the PIR sensor detect the present of a person in the room it communicates with the microcontroller to prepared to receive the measured temperature value from the LM35. Therefore, the LM35 temperature sensor begins to measure the temperature in the room and communicate with the microcontroller with the measure temperature, the microcontroller than communicate with the 16x2 LCD to display the value of the measured temperature. Equations (1), (2) and (3) shows how the measured temperature is converted to a voltage which is been read by the microcontroller. After reading the measure temperature from the LM35 temperature sensor, the microcontroller compares the measured temperature with a reference temperature to determine the appropriate action to be taken. When the reference temperature is greater than the measured temperature the microcontroller triggers the gate of the fan triac to activate the fan by sending pulses of signal. The microcontroller makes use of the difference in value of the measured temperature and the reference temperature to determine the width of pulses to be sent to the fan triac to attain a certain speed of the fan therefore the speed of the fan changes when the measured temperature changes. Also, when measure temperature is less than the reference temperature, the microcontroller triggers the gate of the heater triac to activate the heater by sending pulses of signal. The microcontroller uses the differences in value of the measure temperature and references temperature to determine the width of pulse signal to be sent to the heater

triac to emit a certain level of heat from the heater. Equations (4), (5), (6) and (7) shows the mathematical determination of the width of pulse signal in accordance to the measured temperature. As the measured temperature rises above the reference temperature so does the fan output increase to reduce the room temperature. Whereas, as the measured temperature decrease more below the reference temperature value, so does the heater emit more heat to increase the room temperature.

The LM35 temperature sensor $1^{\circ}\text{C} = 10\text{mV}$

$T = \text{measure temperature in degree centigrade}$

$V_T = \text{Measured temperature voltage read by the microcontoller in mini volt}$

$$\frac{1}{T} = \frac{10}{V_t} \quad (1)$$

Make V_t the subject of the equation

$$1 \times V_t = T \times 10 \quad (2)$$

$$\therefore V_t = 10 \times T \quad (3)$$

When the LM35 measure a temperature of 20°C ($T = 20$) the microcontroller will read a voltage of:

$$V_t = 10 \times 20 = 200\text{mV or } 0.2\text{V}$$

The AC sin wave travel for 20msec at 50Hz for each full cycle. Therefore, after ratification the wave travel for 10ms for each half cycle. The equation below showed mathematically how the microcontroller will control the speed of the fan and regulate the heat from the heater by varying the duty cycles (Duration of wave).

$M_T = \text{Measured temperatur in degree centigrade}$

$R_T =$ Reference temperature in degree centigrade

$D =$ Temperature differnces in degree centigrade

$P_{Dc} =$ Pulse duty cycle in mili seconds

For fan speed control

$$D = M_T - R_T \quad (4)$$

$$P_{Dc} = D \times 0.5 \quad (5)$$

For example when the reference temperature is 24°C and the measure temperature is 30°C

$$D = 30 - 24 = 6^\circ\text{C}$$

$$P_{Dc} = 6 \times 0.5 = 3\text{msec}$$

\therefore The pulse width signal will have a duty cycle of 3msec at 24°C

For heater heat regulation

$$D = M_T - R_T \quad (6)$$

$$P_{Dc} = -D \times 0.5 \quad (7)$$

For example when the reference temperature is 24°C and the measure temperature is 19°C

$$D = 19 - 24 = -5^\circ\text{C}$$

$$P_{Dc} = -(-5) \times 0.5 = 2.5\text{msec}$$

Fig 3-7: Flow chart of room temperature control algorithm

The algorithm function in the following steps:

Step 1: The user will input the reference temperature once using the keypad, but can change it at any time using the keypad.

Step 2: The microcontroller will receive the reference temperature and store it,

Step 3: The microcontroller receives the room temperature from the temperature sensor and display the room temperature and the reference temperature on the LCD.

Step 4: The microcontroller will receive signal from the thermal sensor to know whether or not the room is occupied by a person.

Step 5: When the room is not occupied the algorithm goes back to step3 but when the room is occupied the microcontroller compares the room temperature to the reference temperature.

Step 6: If the room temperature is greater than the reference temperature the microcontroller activates the fan and if the room temperature is less than the reference temperature the microcontroller activates the heater.

Step 7: The microcontroller goes back to step 3 to received the room temperature so as to increase the speed of the fan when the room temperature increases more above the reference and in the case of heater, increase the level of the heater when the room temperature reduces more below the reference temperature.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The analyzes of the automatic room temperature device is depicted in this chapter. The comparison was done by measuring the temperature at day, noon and night time. The analyzes consist of tables and graphs to show the variation of temperature at the different hours of the day and the response of the automatic temperature device.

4.2 RESULT of IMPLEMENTATION

All the stated objective was obtained by the automatic room temperature control.

The table below shown the variation in temperature and the performers of the automatic room temperature control device. The analyses were done by using a reference temperature of 24°C.

Table 1: Table showing the achievement of the control of room temperature.

Hours	Room Temperature	Fan speed	Heat level	Room temperature after device operation
5:00-8:00	20°C	0	20%	22°C
9:00-12:00	25°C	5%	0	23°C
13:00-15:00	30°C	30%	0	28°C
16:00-18:00	30°C – 27°C	30% – 15%	0	26°C
18:00-21:00	25°C	5%	0	23°C
22:00-1:00	21°C	0	15%	23°C

From the table it is seen that, the fan is more in operation than the heater because of the level of temperature and device was able achieve the control of room temperature as seen in the fifth column.

Fig 4-1: graph showing the difference in temperature before and after the device operation

The chart shows the variation in temperature before the automatic room temperature system was operational and after the automatic room temperature device was in operation.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Control of room temperature automatically by varying the speed of the room cooling unit and heat level of the room heating unit. The objectives were:

- To design a fully automated room temperature control system
- To design a temperature controller using a microcontroller
- To write an algorithm to controller a room temperature
- To analyse the performance of the room temperature automated system

As shown in the pervious chapters all the objective was achieved. The fourth objective which is “To analyse the performance of the room temperature automated system” was shown in chapter 4, as seen in the table and chart in chapter 4 the system was able to control the room temperature at different hours of the day when the system was in operation the room temperature changes from either a high value to a low value.

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